

Dyes Derived from Citraconic Acid.

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The object of the present investigation was to prepare dyes from citraconic acid in the same manner as with itaconic acid previously described (Dhar and Dutt, this *Volume*, p. 247), with a view to a systematic determination and comparison of the absorption spectra of the two series of dyestuffs so as to obtain conclusions which can be fitted into the 'Theory of colour on the basis of molecular strain' advanced by one of the present authors (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1871; Dutt, this *Volume*, p. 99).

Citraconic anhydride differs from itaconic anhydride by the position of a double linkage, which, in the former case, is included in a ring system, while in the latter case it belongs to a side chain. It was established by Dutt and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2524) that in the cases of the dialkyl substituted succinic acids, the corresponding fluoresceins have got the following constitution:—

In the case of the fluoresceins of phenyl-succinic acid and methyl-succinic acid, similar constitution was also arrived at by Dutt (unpublished work). Hence from analogy it will be evident that the

structures of resorcinol-itaconein and resorcinol-citraconein are as follows:—

Resorcinol-itaconein.

Resorcinol-citraconein.

Hence when these substances assume quinonoid structures by solution in alkali, their configurations become as follows:—

Resorcinol-itaconein.

Resorcinol-citraconein.

In the above structures the main source of strain is the quinonoid nucleus. Therefore according to the theory of colour, which has been advanced by one of the present authors, any other source of strain besides that will intensify the colour if it is in juxtaposition to the latter. In the two structures of fluoresceins given above it will be seen that the double bond corresponding to the aliphatic acid portion of the molecule is nearer to the quinonoid linkage in the case of resorcinol-citraconein, while in the case of resorcinol-itaconein it is one position further off. This will account for the fact that the absorption maxima of resorcinol-citraconein is slightly greater than that of resorcinol-itaconein. In a systematic comparison of the absorption maxima of the two series of dyestuffs, it has also been found that, in general, dyes derived from citraconic acid are always more absorptive than the corresponding dyes derived from itaconic acid. In the table of absorption maxima which has been appended it will be found that the only exceptional case in this connection is hexabromo-resorcinol-itaconein, which is slightly more

absorptive than tetrabromo-resorcinol-citraconein. But this can be easily accounted for by the presence in the former of two extra bromine atoms.

Phenol-citraconein has already been prepared and described by Krishna and Pope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 280). With the exception of this no other dyestuffs have been obtained from citraconic acid by condensation with aromatic amino or hydroxy compounds. The following aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds have therefore been condensed with citraconic acid and the corresponding dyestuff obtained:—resorcinol, catechol, phloroglucinol, pyrogallol and *m*-diethylamidophenol. The compound with resorcinol has also been brominated and the corresponding tetra-bromo compound obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The condensations of citraconic acid with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds have been effected exactly in the same way as in the cases of the corresponding itaconeins (Dhar and Dutt, *loc. cit.*). The results are summarised below.

The Citraconeins.

Name.	Appearance.	M.p.	Colour in alkali.	Colour of fluorescence.	Analysis (calc. % in brackets).
Phenol-	... Light yellow prisms	160°	Pinkish red	...	C, 72.11(72.34) H, 4.7(4.9)
Resorcinol-	... Yellow needles	217°	Orange red	Yellow-green	C, 68.58(68.91) H, 4.2(4.0)
Phloroglucinol-		Above 290°	Deep red	...	C, 61.75(62.19) H, 3.6(3.6)
Catechol-	... Colourless prisms	260°	Pink	...	C, 68.71(68.91) H, 4.4(4.0)
Pyrogallol-	... Dark brown needles	230°	Brown	...	C, 62.02(62.19) H, 3.9(3.6)
Tetrabromo-resorcinol-	... Dark red needles	190°	Deep pink	Yellow	Br, 52.6(52.2)
<i>m</i> -Diethylamido-phenol-	... Reddish violet prisms	98°	Bluish red	Yellowish brown	N, 8.0(7.8)

Absorption Maxima of the Citraconeins and the Itaconeins.

C=Citraconein; I=Itaconein. Figures indicate approximate wave-lengths.

	Phenol-C.	Phenol-I.	Resor- cinol-C.	Resor- cinol-I.	Tetra- bromo- resor- cinol-C.	Hexa- bromo- resor- cinol-I.
In alcohol	4270	4290	4870	4880	5450	5480
Do, with KOH	5530	5410	4940	4880	5490	5610
	<i>m</i> -Diethylamidophenol-C.			<i>m</i> -Diethylamidophenol-I.		
In alcohol		5540			5460	
Do, with HCl		5560			5470	

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